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ANALYSIS OF CLINICAL, IMMUNOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS C DEPENDING ON THE VIRUS GENOTYPE

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Summary. Bazhora Yuri, Gudz Valentyn, Huseinova Leila, Mozgova Valentina, Usychenko Kateryna. **ANALYSIS OF CLINICAL, IMMUNOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS C DEPENDING ON THE VIRUS GENOTYPE.** – The Odessa National Medical University; e-mail: usichenko2006@gmail.com. HCV infection is one of the main causes of chronic liver diseases, the development of liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. **The purpose:** to analyze immunological and biochemical parameters in chronic hepatitis C patients depending on the genotype of the virus. **Materials and methods.** 100 chronic HC patients aged 18-62 y.o., have been examined; their were 56 women and 44 men. The control group included 30 practically healthy middle-aged individuals. The concentration of total bilirubin and its fraction, the activity of AlAt and AsAt, the concentration of total protein, albumin and globulin, prothrombin index, and alkaline phosphatase were assessed. A qualitative and quantitative determination of viral RNA was carried out in all patients with RCR. The genotype of the hepatitis C virus was also determined using the polymerase chain reaction method (1 (1a and 1b), 2, 3 (3a 3b), 4, 5, 6). Subpopulations of B and T lymphocytes (CD3+, CD4+, CD8+, CD16+, CD19+) were determined by immunofluorescence method. **Conclusions:** it can be assumed that the genotype of the virus 1a and 1b causes more pronounced changes in biochemical parameters and indicators of the immunological status than the virus of the 3rd genotype.

Key words: chronic hepatitis C, clinical, immunological, biochemical parameters, virus genotype.

Реферат. Бажора Ю., Гудзь В., Гусейнова Л., Мозгова В., Усиченко К. **АНАЛІЗ КЛІНІЧНИХ, ІМУНОЛОГІЧНИХ ТА БІОХІМІЧНИХ ПОКАЗНИКІВ У ХВОРИХ НА ХРОНІЧНИЙ ГЕПАТИТ С ЗАЛЕЖНО ВІД ГЕНОТИПУ ВІРУСУ.** Хронічний вірусний гепатит С є однією з основних причин хронічних захворювань печінки, розвитку цирозу печінки та гепатоцелюлярної карциноми. **Мета:** проаналізувати імунологічні та біохімічні показники у хворих на хронічний гепатит С залежно від генотипу вірусу. **Матеріали та методи.** Обстежено 100 хворих на ХГ С віком 18-62 роки; 56 жінок і 44 чоловіка.

Контрольну групу склали 30 практично здорових осіб середнього віку. Визначали концентрацію загального білірубину та його фракції, активність АІАт та АsАт, концентрацію загального білка, альбуміну та глобуліну, протромбіновий індекс, лужну фосфатазу. Усім хворим проводили якісне та кількісне визначення вірусної РНК. Також методом полімеразної ланцюгової реакції визначали генотип вірусу гепатиту С (1 (1a і 1b), 2, 3 (3a, 3b), 4, 5, 6). Імунофлюоресцентним методом визначали субпопуляції В- і Т-лімфоцитів (CD3+, CD4+, CD8+, CD16+, CD19+). **Висновки:** можна припустити, що генотип вірусу 1a та 1b викликає більш виражені зміни біохімічних показників та показників імунологічного статусу, ніж вірус 3-го генотипу.

Ключові слова: хронічний гепатит С, клінічні, імунологічні, біохімічні показники, генотип вірусу.

Introduction

HCV infection is one of the main causes of chronic liver diseases, the development of liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. According to WHO, 3-4 million people are infected annually in all the world, and 200 million patients have a chronic form of the disease. In Ukraine, about 1 million people are infected with HCV [1, 2].

According to many researchers, the pathogenetic features of chronic hepatitis C are determined by the interaction of two main factors: the characteristics of the human body and the structure of HCV (pathogen). The characteristics of the body include the nature of the immune response [3].

Several mechanisms of the suppressive effect of chronic hepatitis C on the immune response are known: changes in the functional activity of cytotoxic lymphocytes, mutations of the HCV genome, direct action of HCV proteins on T cells, and others. The basis of immunological reactions in chronic hepatitis C is an imbalance of Th1\Th2 with a shift towards the Th2 subpopulation, as well as changes in cytokine regulation [4].

The outcome of HCV infection largely depends on the nature of the immune response. In the immunopathogenesis of CHC, the role of individual cells of the immune system has also been established. It is so significant that the population of NK cells has a leading role in the chronicization of hepatitis of viral etiology and in the development of liver fibrosis [5].

One of the main characteristics of HCV is its genotype. Based on different nucleotide sequences of genomic RNA, 6 genotypes are distinguished, and according to some data, 7-11 genotypes and about 100 subtypes. In Ukraine, genotypes 1b and 3a predominate. It has been shown that achieving a sustained virological response depends on the HCV genotype, the stage of liver fibrosis, and the initial level of viral load [6].

Recent studies have shown that chronic hepatitis C caused by genotype 3 virus has a number of pathogenetic features. It has been established that the rate of fibrosis progression in patients with HCV genotype 3 is significantly higher than in those infected with genotypes 1, 2 and 4. This is probably due to the greater production of proinflammatory cytokines in patients with genotype 2 [7]. According to a number of authors, the combination of hepatic steatosis induced by the HCV genotype 3 virus with a characteristic high viral load affects the course of the disease and reduces the effectiveness of antiviral therapy [8].

Thus, there is a relationship between HCV genotypes, the nature of the immune response, and the progression of liver fibrosis. However, studies on immunological parameters and cytokine profile depending on the genotype are few.

The purpose of this work is the analysis of immunological and biochemical parameters in patients with chronic hepatitis C depending on the genotype of the virus.

Materials and methods

100 patients with chronic hepatitis were examined; their age was 18-62 years. All examined patients who were included in the study are observed in the hepatology center of the Municipal Clinical Infectious Hospital. The number of women and men examined was almost the same, 56 and 44 people, respectively.

The control group included 30 practically healthy middle-aged individuals. The number of men and women was the same (15 people).

In all patients, such biochemical parameters as the concentration of total bilirubin and its fraction, the activity of AlAt and AsAt, the concentration of total protein, albumin and globulin, prothrombin index, and alkaline phosphatase were assessed.

In order to confirm the diagnosis, a qualitative and quantitative determination of viral RNA was carried out in all patients using the polymerase chain reaction method. The genotype of the hepatitis C virus was also determined using the polymerase chain reaction method (1 (1a and 1b), 2, 3 (3a 3b), 4, 5, 6).

Subpopulations of B and T lymphocytes (CD3+, CD4+, CD8+, CD16+, CD19+) were determined by immunofluorescence method using a set of polyclonal and monoclonal antibodies to establish differential antigens of human lymphocytes using a Eurostar immunofluorescence microscope.

The relationship between the hepatitis C virus genotype and biochemical parameters, as well as the subpopulation composition of peripheral blood, was assessed using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. Comparison of biochemical and immunological parameters in healthy and sick individuals was carried out using the Mann-Whitney test.

Results and its discussion

The distribution of patients with chronic hepatitis C depending on the genotype is presented in Figure 1.

Figure. 1 Distribution of patients depending on the genotype of the hepatitis C virus.

In the group of patients with chronic hepatitis C, patients with genotypes 1b and 3a predominated; the number of patients with genotypes 2 was lower.

When establishing a diagnosis of chronic hepatitis, anamnestic data and clinical manifestations were taken into account: weakness, increased fatigue, reduced work capacity, malaise, sweating, skin itching, decreased or absent appetite, nausea, a feeling of heaviness in the right hypochondrium, unstable stools, jaundice, manifestations of hemorrhagic syndrome (bleeding gums, hematomas at injection sites, hemorrhagic rash on the skin, epistaxis), hepatomegaly, splenomegaly.

The clinical course of chronic hepatitis of viral etiology was characterized by periods of aggravation and subsidence of certain symptoms, however, all patients before the start of antiviral treatment emphasized significant changes in their general condition, which reduced the quality of life. No statistically significant difference in clinical symptoms was revealed in patients with different genotypes of the hepatitis C virus.

Analysis of biochemical parameters in patients with chronic hepatitis C with different genotypes is presented in Table 1.

An analysis of some immunological parameters in patients with CHC with different genotypes is presented in Table 2.

Table 1.

Biochemical parameters in patients with chronic hepatitis C depending on the genotype of the virus ($M \pm m$).

Indicators	Patients with chronic hepatitis C, genotype 1a and 1b, n=51	Patients with chronic hepatitis C, genotype 2 and 3a, n=41
Total bilirubin, $\mu\text{mol/l}$	19.2 ± 1.42	18.4 ± 1.32
AlAt, mmol/l	3.28 ± 0.69	$2.89 \pm 0.21^*$
AsAt, mmol/l	2.35 ± 0.18	$1.84 \pm 0.15^*$
Thymol test, units	8.7 ± 0.05	9.1 ± 0.03
Total protein, g/l	65.14 ± 0.71	65.64 ± 0.68
Albumin, g/l	37.64 ± 0.66	38.22 ± 0.54
Globulins γ , g/l	7.22 ± 0.19	7.68 ± 0.15
Prothrombin index	96.04 ± 0.38	97.04 ± 0.31

* – the difference in indicators in the comparison groups is statistically significant ($P < 0.05$)

In the group of patients with chronic hepatitis C caused by genotypes 1a and 1b, higher level of alanine aminotransferase and aspartate aminotransferase were observed than in the group of patients with CHC caused by viruses of the 2nd and 3rd genotypes.

Table 2.

Immunological parameters in patients with CHC depending on the genotype of the virus ($M \pm m$).

Indicators	Control group, n = 30	Patients with chronic hepatitis C, genotype 1a and 1b, n=51	Patients with chronic hepatitis C, genotype 2 and 3a, n=41
CD3+, %	71.8 ± 1.92	30.25 ± 3.54	34.29 ± 4.22
CD3+, abc.	0.78 ± 0.06	0.39 ± 0.04	0.40 ± 0.02
CD4+, %	41.2 ± 1.5	$25.86 \pm 3.89^*$	$28.96 \pm 4.32^*$
CD4+, abc.	0.48 ± 0.02	$0.38 \pm 0.02^*$	$0.48 \pm 0.04^*$
CD8+, %	20.5 ± 1.3	25.06 ± 4.21	23.06 ± 3.48
CD8+, abc.	0.22 ± 0.02	0.15 ± 0.22	0.16 ± 0.21
CD16+, %	14.1 ± 1.6	$6.62 \pm 2.41^*$	$8.91 \pm 2.31^*$
CD16+, abc.	0.22 ± 0.07	$0.11 \pm 0.04^*$	$0.14 \pm 0.03^*$
CD19+, %	10.8 ± 1.2	$14.23 \pm 2.80^*$	$16.21 \pm 3.21^*$
CD19+, abc	0.24 ± 0.19	$0.29 \pm 0.13^*$	$0.26 \pm 0.13^*$

* – the difference in indicators is statistically significant in comparison with the control group ($P < 0.05$)

In the group of patients with chronic hepatitis C caused by genotypes 1a and 1b, more pronounced changes in cellular immunity were observed than in the group of patients with CHC caused by viruses of the 2nd and 3rd genotypes.

To assess the relationship between nonparametric (hepatitis C virus genotype) and parametric (biochemical and immunological parameters) data, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used.

The following patterns have been identified:

- weak positive (direct) relationship between the genotype of the virus and the percentage of CD3+, CD4+ and CD16+ (patients with CHC caused by genotypes 1a and 1b have lower numbers of CD3+, CD4+ and CD16+ than patients with CHC caused by genotypes 2 and 3) ;

- weak negative (inverse) relationship between the genotype of the virus and the percentage of CD8+ and CD19+ (patients with CHC caused by genotypes 1a and 1b have a higher number of CD8+ and CD19+ than patients with CHC caused by genotypes 2 and 3);

- moderate negative (inverse) relationship between the genotype of the virus and the

activity of ALT and AST (patients with CHC caused by genotypes 1a and 1b have higher transaminase activity than patients with CHC caused by genotypes 2 and 3).

conclusions

As a result of the studies, it can be assumed that the genotype of the virus 1a and 1b causes more pronounced changes in biochemical parameters and indicators of the immunological status than the virus of the 3rd genotype.

It is possible that the genotype of the virus influences the rate of fibrosis progression, which will be the subject of our further research.

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